

BGS Website Redesign: simplifying data access through intuitive design

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

The British Geological Survey has recently redesigned its website improving the **Data menu and Data search** by focusing more on usability and accessibility. The Data menu now has an intuitive structure. New primary-level themes have been added and this helped categorise the secondary level in a more user-friendly way. The introduction of sectors, data by subjects, and data application categories will enable users to find the specific information that they are looking for in a faster way.

The data search page is also redesigned with a user-friendly interface, including new filters, a responsive search bar, a new dataset description template, and the introduction of new tags to show availability through API geo index and sector.

Overall, the modifications satisfy the target audience of BGS which includes researchers, industries, and the general public. This aims to provide improved features and user experience for the diverse user groups.

Rationale for the work

Why does BGS need improved data access on the website? While talking to both the internal team (informatics team, products team, enquiry team, data stewards, communications, business development and licensing) and external audience the following pain points have emerged:

- A complex network of menus
- Terminologies are confusing even to the internal audience
- Users need to scroll right to the bottom of a page to get the important link that they are looking for.
- The full data catalogue (Standard geo network catalogue) is difficult or impossible to find
- Users think the current catalogue is a full list of our datasets, whereas it is only selected datasets.
- Relations between NERC, NGDC, and EDS are not clear.
- Difficulty in searching for required datasets

The proposed changes aim to address the above issues and improve the overall user experience by making it easier for people to discover, access, and use BGS data.

Methodology

The brief was to redesign the BGS website data menu section by addressing the following points:

- Design an intuitive journey to the target audience by grouping data-related content.
- What are the most important services that we need to promote
- Remove the redundancy and agree on the terminology
- Improve BGS data search

Target audience

- Data scientist: Import and access data
- Data artist: Create graphs, charts and other infographics using data
- Policymaker: Find research papers
- Developers: Looking for application programming interfaces (API)
- Researchers: Access to raw data
- General public

Design Process

User research

The user research is mainly carried out by talking to many stakeholders. **User interviews** are done with the enquiry team, products team, database and architecture team. The interview insights helped to draw the main user needs and pain points. The following areas contain most of the pain points:

- Data search on the BGS website
- Standards based on Geonetwork catalogue
- Terminology and grouping of certain datasets based on themes
- Clarity on NGDC deposited data search
- Frustrations while using geo index map viewer

A **Heuristic evaluation** of the BGS website data section has been carried out to inspect the usability issues on the interface. During the evaluation, it was found that certain sections were overwhelming. This requires providing additional documentation to the users. Data search is not intuitive to navigate, and therefore, the need for an advanced filter is clear. While navigating through certain pages, error prevention is missing.

Ideation

After gathering information from interviews, a workgroup (internal stakeholders) has formed to draw a new site map for the BGS data menu section. A **card sorting activity** is conducted among the work group members. Primary-level and secondary-level themes are already provided to the participants. The options were from the existing structure and new ones identified from the interviews. Participants created an information architecture by having an active discussion. This has gone through a couple of iterations and the final one has been produced.

Improvements made

1. Reduced the number of primary-level options. This will make it easier for users to find what they are looking for and reduce unnecessary scrolling.

2. Introduction of new themes. According to the users, the demand sector is introduced as a separate theme.
3. Differentiated the new dataset search along with existing popular data catalogues (metadata catalogue, Geoindex)
4. National Geographic Repository is combined with NGDC and depositing data needs standalone attention by having a separate primary level.
5. Map viewers and Technologies have been combined so all the data can be accessed by a variety of themes under data by subject.

Wireframes/visual design

Improvements to the user experience of searching for BGS data. This will involve updating the search page filters and layout, improving the dataset descriptions, and providing a clear link to the metadata catalogue.

Frequent meetings with the workgroup gave the ideas for the new design. This was an iterative process and finally got an agreement on what datasets, functions and labels need to be added to the new data search catalogue.

We identified several issues with the current data search page that make it difficult for users to find, access and use BGS data effectively. These issues include:

- Drop-down filters could be made more relevant to user groups.
- Search results presentation is difficult to scan and could be made more visual and user friendly.

- Difficult to know which datasets are new or recently updated.
- Limited opportunities to promote or highlight certain datasets.
- Complex dataset description template.
- Lack of clarity on dataset availability through APIs.
- Uncertainty about which datasets are viewable on GeoIndex.

Updated search page

Below we detail the changes made to the search page:

The screenshot shows the BGS Dataset Search interface. Annotations point to specific features:

- Updated list of filters:** Points to the filter dropdowns for 'All themes', 'All sectors', 'All Access Types', and 'All License Types'.
- Links to full metadata catalogue:** Points to the 'BGS Metadata Catalogue' link below the search bar.
- Highlights new/updated datasets:** Points to orange 'UPDATED' tags on the dataset cards.
- Tags to show dataset availability through API and Geoindex:** Points to 'API Available' and 'Map Preview' tags.
- tags to show sector and dataset bundle:** Points to 'THEME', 'SECTOR', and 'COLLECTION' tags on the dataset cards.

1. The new additions to the filters are **Sectors**, **Access type** (allows users to search by API, Download, Map view-based datasets), **Licence types** (Open, premium) and **Themes**.
2. We made the metadata catalogue link more visible which was crucial. It also states users can visit there to find a comprehensive list of all BGS data.
3. An update to the search page layout involves a shift from a list-based display of search results to a card-based layout. Each card will represent a single dataset and display key information, including the title, type, description, themes, license, coverage, API availability, and a direct link to view the dataset on GeoIndex (if applicable). This new design is responsive across all devices (desktop, tablet, mobile).

UPDATED

BGS Civils

The BGS Civils collection offers comprehensive geological datasets tailored for the civil engineering sector, providing key attributes like texture, structure, and engineering parameters in a modular GIS format.

ENGINEERING GEOLOGY
ENGINEERING
CIVILS COLLECTION

Premium • Great Britain • API Available • Map Preview

Access

STATUS

AGS Utilities Tool

The AGS utilities tool offers schema validation, data validation and conversion of geotechnical AGS files. The API is publicly available for use in stakeholders' own analysis, processing or software.

TYPE
THEME
SECTOR
BUNDLE
TYPE

Licence Type • Coverage • API Available • Map Preview

Access

STATUS

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Access

4. The update to the BGS dataset description template will improve its layout and presentation to make it look more modern and easier to find key information about the datasets, using existing BGS website components where possible.

BGS Geology 50K

GIS polygon data

1:50 000 ENGLAND WALES LICENSED

Generalised digital geological map data based on BGS's New Series 1:50 000 and 1:63 360-scale (one-inch to one-mile) maps with updated nomenclature, including a few 1:100 000-scale maps of Orkney and the Hebrides.

Many BGS geology maps are now available digitally. The Digital Geological Map of Great Britain project (formerly known as DIGMapGB) has prepared 1:625 000, 1:250 000, 1:50 000 and 1:10 000-scale datasets for England, Wales and Scotland. Work continues to upgrade these.

[Download the User Guide](#)

Sample Map Download Access Data

Key Information	Description	Support documentation	Insights
<p>Scale: 1:50 000</p> <p>Coverage: England and Wales</p> <p>Availability: Open data(Viewable only) / Premium data</p> <p>Version: Latest version and links to previous ones</p> <p>Price: Free: Available to view as a WMS layer or via the onshore Geolindex. Licence: £0.21 per km² for commercial use. Subject to number of users, licence fee and data preparation fee</p>			
		<p>Format: GIS polygon data (ESRI, Mapinfo, others available by request)</p> <p>Uses: Local-level to Region-level use</p>	

5. Created a homepage for dataset bundles designed to meet the needs of various sectors. This involved making a new homepage with an overview of all the sectors and A separate homepage for each sector.

The British Geological Survey (BGS) offers a **range of comprehensive datasets** designed to meet the needs of various sectors, including property development, lending, insurance, and environmental management. Our products provide valuable insights into ground conditions, geological hazards, and environmental factors, empowering you to make informed decisions and mitigate risks. All the datasets are classified under sectors, if you cant find your sector please [contact us](#).

Our Vision:
We support various industries with out innovative solutions and services.

Our sectors

- Insurance/Lenders**
An insurer will need to understand the presence of risk, likelihood of a claim and how that translates into financial risk.
→ Explore
- Lenders**
Lenders rely on geological data to assess risks and opportunities in property investments, ensuring informed decisions that can lead to sustainable growth.
→ Explore
- Planners/developers**
Planning applications, mineral resource assessment, brownfield assessment, EIA
→ Explore

User testing

User testing is an essential part of the BGS website redesign process. Involving real users in the testing process can ensure the website is usable, accessible, and meets the needs of its diverse audience. User testing provides valuable feedback on design choices. Does the new layout and visual design resonate with users? Are they able to easily find and understand the information they need? Real users often interact with websites in ways designers and developers might not anticipate. User testing helps identify usability problems like confusing navigation, unclear instructions, or difficult-to-find information. The BGS website serves a diverse audience, including those with disabilities. User testing with individuals who use assistive technologies can help ensure the website is accessible to everyone. This is an iterative process. The feedback will be incorporated into the design process.

Lessons learnt

- **User-centred design is the key** - By involving users in the design process, it was convenient to identify the needs and pain points while using the BGS website data section. Conducting extensive user research, interviews and usability testing are part of the process.
- **Data discovery is difficult** - The website has various data and it is challenging for the users to find out exactly what they are looking for. The intuitive new datasearch and improved data menu will help users to navigate easily.
- **Continuous improvement is essential** - The redesign of the BGS website is an ongoing process. It is necessary to monitor the feedback and make iterative improvements to the website.
- **Collaboration is magic** - The redesign process involved users/stakeholders from a multidisciplinary background. By working together, it is expected to deliver a high-quality website meeting everyone's needs.
- **Accessibility is important** - The BGS has a diverse range of users, and to ensure everyone can access the website it is important to adhere to accessibility standards. The website should have assistive technologies and different forms of data.

Opportunities and future recommendations

- Conduct user testing with the target audience and improve the information architecture and design.
- In the long term, we plan to switch to Geonetwork for our metadata management. This will simplify our content management for data products and ensure consistency across different BGS systems, by having a single source of truth. This is done by getting the metadata catalogue ready to work with selected datasets. Also, using the metadata catalogue to populate the search results and new template.
- Expand the same user research on other sections of the website (Research, BGS online shop, discovering geology). Redesign the entire website.
- Implement analytics on the redesigned BGS website and measure the conversions and success rate. Also, get the feedback from the enquiry team.
- Improve the visibility of data resellers on the BGS website. Consider improving the data delivery by understanding the user's needs.
- Consider how to make data and information easier to access using AI tools (large language models). More and more people will be using AI tools in the future so we should make BGS data and information accessible using them.